

COMMUNITY-CENTRIC DIGITAL PRESERVATION: COLLABORATIVE MODEL FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE ASIA-PACIFIC

Goki Miyakita

*Keio Museum Commons
Japan*

*5ki-miyakita@keio.jp
0000-0001-8640-533X*

Eliko Akashi

*Keio University
Japan*

*akashieliko@keio.jp
0000-0003-3692-5024*

Alinuer Yimin

*Keio University
Japan*

*alanur2025@keio.jp
0009-0002-0478-1900*

Keiko Okawa

*Keio University
Japan*

*keiko@keio.jp
0000-0003-3310-5020*

Abstract – This paper presents a collaborative, community-led model for the ethical and sustainable digital preservation of cultural heritage in the diverse Asia-Pacific (APAC). Drawing from the work-in-progress of the SOI Asia and DHASH project, we detail how community centrality fosters interdisciplinary collaboration. Through case studies in Indonesia and Nepal, we explore how this engagement shapes preservation outcomes and discuss the potential of this framework to build an inclusive Open Science infrastructure for Digital Humanities in the APAC.

Submission Type – Short Paper

Keywords – Preservation Action, Collaboration, Community, Open Science, Asia Pacific

Conference Topics – Tūhono - Connect

I. INTRODUCTION

The Asia-Pacific (APAC) region presents a unique and complex landscape for digital cultural heritage preservation. Its diversity encompasses a vast array of tangible and intangible heritage, from ancient monuments to living traditions, languages, and rituals. However, this richness is often coupled with vulnerability. Factors such as rapid modernization, environmental change, political instability, and the sheer vastness of the region threaten the

preservation of these cultural resources [1], [2]. Furthermore, historical contexts, including colonialism and subsequent economic disparities, have often led to the underrepresentation and marginalization of certain cultural narratives within global heritage discourses [3], [4].

While digital technologies are invaluable for documentation and preservation, technological solutions alone cannot fully address the complexities involved [5], [6]. The uncritical application of digital methods can risk perpetuating existing inequalities, imposing external frameworks, or decontextualizing heritage from its living cultural environment [7]. There is a growing consensus, particularly within the Digital Humanities (DH), that ethical and effective digital preservation must be deeply rooted in the communities whose heritage is being represented [3], [4], [8].

This paper explores a community-centric model for digital preservation that is emerging from the ongoing work of the School on Internet Asia (SOI Asia) and its DH-focused project, DHASH (Digital Humanities Asia/And Scientific Hub). Rather than presenting a prescriptive paper, we aim to discuss

the challenges and opportunities of this approach, presenting two examples from our work as a way to illustrate how these challenges are beginning to be addressed. Drawing from our case studies in Indonesia (Aceh, Malang) and Nepal, we will show how a community-centric framework fosters collaboration and helps build a more equitable, sustainable digital heritage for the region.

II. BACKGROUND : A FOUNDATION OF COLLABORATION AND OPENNESS

The foundation for this community-centric model lies in the long-standing collaborative network fostered by the SOI Asia. Launched in 2001, SOI Asia has grown into a consortium connecting 29 universities and institutions across 13 APAC countries [9], [10]. Initially focused on STEM education and building internet infrastructure, SOI Asia cultivated a culture of cross-border partnership and knowledge sharing. This ecosystem is strengthened by key projects: SARENA-PAC and ARENA-PAC ensuring a robust network backbone, the APIE program building internet engineering capacity, and the EBA program fostering collaborative problem-solving through fieldwork (Fig. 1).

This established network provides a fertile ground for implementing the principles of Open Science (OS), which, as promoted by UNESCO, emphasize transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in research [11]. While OS offers great potential, its application in the humanities, particularly in diverse, non-Western contexts, faces hurdles [12], [13]. Challenges include adapting standardized frameworks to diverse data types, ensuring multilingual support [14], and navigating complex ethical considerations.

It is at this intersection—the collaborative network of SOI Asia and the principles of OS that the DHASH project emerged, aiming to build a community-centric OS infrastructure for DH in the APAC region.

Figure 1. Overview of SOI Asia Structure

III. WHY COMMUNITY MUST LEAD: FOSTERING COLLABORATION THROUGH OPENNESS

A community-first approach to preserving cultural heritage necessitates collaboration across multiple institutional and disciplinary layers, embodying the core tenets of OS.

A. Inter-institutional Collaboration

Effective community work requires partnerships with local institutions (universities, museums, cultural centers) that have established relationships and trust. The SOI Asia network provides the framework for such partnerships, connecting researchers with local academic partners like Syiah Kuala University, Brawijaya University (both located in Indonesia), and Tribhuvan University (located in Nepal) in the DHASH project [1], [2]. This structure facilitates resource sharing, logistical support, and a deeper understanding of local contexts.

B. Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Representing cultural heritage in its full complexity demands insights from various disciplines. A community-centric approach naturally fosters this convergence. Our DHASH case studies exemplify this, requiring collaboration among diverse experts to document tombstones, temples, and musical traditions (Fig. 2). This process is a practical application of OS, where knowledge is co-created by:

- *Humanities Scholars* (historians, archaeologists, anthropologists, etc.) who provide contextual understanding.
- *Community Experts* (elders, artisans, ritual specialists, etc.) who offer invaluable local knowledge and cultural significance.
- *Technologists* (computer scientists, engineers, etc.) who provide expertise in digitization, data management, and platform development.
- *Social Scientists* who contribute insights into community dynamics and ethical considerations.
- *Designers* who focus on creating user-friendly and inclusive interfaces for exploring digital heritage [15].

Figure 2. [LEFT] 3D scanned tombstones at Aceh, [MIDDLE] 3D-documented temples in Malang, [RIGHT] Photo of the recording of Nepal's Sarangi

IV. COMMUNITY-CENTRIC PRESERVATION IN ACTION: LESSONS FROM THE FIELD

Through DHASH, the SOI Asia demonstrates how digital preservation can be both community-driven and attuned to local cultural contexts. The model is built on three pillars:

1) *Collaborative Foundation*: SOI Asia's multi-institutional network fosters trust and enables shared infrastructure (ARENA-PAC) and capacity building (CBR, EBA, APIE) where digital preservation efforts are anchored in long-standing relationships and local institutional knowledge.

2) *Ethical Partnership for Heritage Preservation*: DHASH partners with local communities from the outset. Projects in Aceh, Malang, and Nepal involve collaborative fieldwork, ethical engagement, and capacity building, empowering local voices to decentralize historical narratives.

3) *Inclusive Design for Access*: The DHASH digital archive utilizes open-source tools (such as Omeka and Voyager [16], [17]) focusing on "generous interfaces" [18] and human-centered design for accessibility across diverse audiences (Fig. 3).

This model illustrates how culturally grounded, collaboratively developed, and inclusively designed OS infrastructures can guide long-term, sustainable digital heritage efforts throughout APAC.

Figure 3. Experimenting Omeka and Voyager

V. DISCUSSION: ADDRESSING THE CHALLENGE OF LONG-TERM DIGITAL PRESERVATION

Developing a sustainable, community-centric OS infrastructure for DH in APAC requires addressing significant challenges, particularly concerning the

long-term preservation and governance of digital assets.

- *Digital Divide and Accessibility*: Unequal access to technology and internet connectivity remains a major barrier. The OS infrastructure must incorporate low-bandwidth options and prioritize user-friendly design.
- *Data Standardization*: Finding common standards for metadata and data formats is crucial for interoperability (e.g., FAIR principles), yet must accommodate the vast linguistic and cultural diversity of APAC without imposing homogenizing frameworks [14]. Community input is vital to this process.
- *Intellectual Property and Ethics*: Navigating ownership, access rights, and ethical use of culturally sensitive materials requires robust frameworks developed in close consultation with source communities. In our project, the community is involved in ongoing dialogues to determine who can access the digital records, under what conditions, and how they can be used in the future.
- *Sustainability*: A critical question is what happens after a project is 'completed.' The DHASH platform, built on the robust research and education network; SOI Asia, serves as the primary repository. However, long-term preservation is a shared responsibility and we must ensure stewardship and data curation beyond initial project funding cycles by empowering our local institutional partners to integrate these digital assets into their own established preservation frameworks.

VI. CONCLUSION

The ongoing work of SOI Asia and DHASH highlights a promising model for advancing digital cultural heritage preservation across the APAC. Placing communities at the core of these efforts is not only ethically imperative but also strategically essential for ensuring relevance, accuracy, and long-term sustainability. This approach naturally fosters the open and interdisciplinary collaboration required to grapple with the complexity of cultural heritage in this diverse region.

The development of a dedicated, community-centric OS infrastructure for DH represents a critical next step, aiming to provide a sustainable platform for preserving and sharing the region's underrepresented narratives. Such efforts return the right of narration to the community itself, allowing them to tell their own stories on a global platform. The challenges are significant, but by intertwining diverse disciplines and connecting communities, we can create a more inclusive, representative, and vibrant digital heritage landscape for the APAC and beyond.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Miyakita and E. Akashi, "SOI (School on Internet) Asia's Initiatives in Digitizing Cultural Resources in the Asia-Pacific Region," [in Japanese] *The KeMCo Review* 03, 2025.
- [2] A. Yimin et al., "Digitizing and Visualizing Cultural Heritage in Asia: The DHASH Project's Approach to Digital Archive," 2025, unpublished.
- [3] D. Roy and N. Menon, "No Making, Not Now: Decolonizing Digital Humanities in South Asia," [Epub], in *Global Debates in the Digital Humanities*. University of Minnesota Press, 2022, pp. 996-1044.
- [4] D. Luo et al., "Asian perspectives: Cultural identities and religious aura in recent DH projects from China, India, and Indonesia," presented at DH2024, Washington, D.C., 2024.
- [5] M. Leigh, M. Gallinger, V. Zakuta, J. Barrera-Gomez, and S. Abrams, "The Future of Preservation: Reinventing the Repository at Harvard," in *iPRES 2024 Papers*, 2024.
- [6] J. Weatherburn, "The Flux and Rhythm of Community: A Case Study on Building and Sustaining a Community of Practice," in *iPRES 2024 Papers*, 2024.
- [7] A. Okune, R. Hillyer, D. Albornoz, A. Posada, and L. Chan, "Whose Infrastructure? Towards Inclusive and Collaborative Knowledge Infrastructures in Open Science," presented at ELPUB 2018, Toronto, Canada, Jun 2018.
- [8] Webb, S. et al., "Feminist Digital Humanities: Theoretical, Social, and Material Engagements," *Full Stack Feminism in Digital Humanities*, 2023.
- [9] K. Okawa, "Global education for global issues: Lessons learned from SOI ASIA project," presented at Int. symposium on Global Campus for Sustainability Education, Hokkaido University, Japan, Oct. 29, 2010.
- [10] E. Akashi, G. Miyakita, and K. Okawa, "Fostering a Culture of Inclusive and Fair Open Science Infrastructure in the Asia Pacific," presented at Digital Humanities 2023. Collaboration as Opportunity (DH2023), Graz, Austria, 2023.
- [11] UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, "UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science," 2021.
- [12] M. Knöchelmann, "Open science in the humanities, or: Open humanities?," *Publications*, vol. 7, no. 4, p. 65, 2019.
- [13] P. Longley Arthur and L. Hearn, "Toward open research: A narrative review of the challenges and opportunities for open humanities," *Journal of Communication*, vol. 71, no. 5, pp. 827-853, 2021.
- [14] COAR Task Force on Supporting Multilingualism and non-English Content in Repositories, "Good practice advice for managing multilingual and non-English language content in repositories," COAR, 2023.
- [15] G. Miyakita, "Human-Centered Approach in Designing a Digital Archive in the Age of Open Science: Case Study of Keio Object Hub," *KeMCo Review* 1, pp. 183-194, Keio University, 2023.
- [16] C. Boyles, "AREPR and Omeka S: Developing Tools for the DH Community," Michigan State University, 2022.
- [17] S. Schreibman, K. Schoueri, and C. Papadopoulos, "Storytelling in 3D: Designing Interactive Digital Narratives," in *Proc. 27th Int. Conf. Cultural Heritage and New Technologies*, Heidelberg, 2022.
- [18] M. Whitelaw, "Towards Generous Interfaces for Archival Collections," in *Proc. Digital Humanities Australasia Conf.*, 2012, no. 2, pp. 123-132.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Goki Miyakita, Ph.D., Senior Assistant Professor at Keio Museum Commons, specializes in user-experience design and digital public humanities.

Eliko Akashi, Ph.D., Project Senior Assistant Professor at Keio University, researches collaborative learning and digital inclusion.

Alinuer Yimin, Ph.D., Project Assistant Professor at Keio University, conducts research on Object-based Learning, museum education, and the implementation of inclusive frameworks in practice.

Keiko Okawa, Ph.D., Advanced Research Project Professor at Keio University, serves as the academic lead and director of the SOI Asia.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is funded by the Asia Pacific Network Information Centre (APNIC) Foundation. We would like to thank all SOI Asia members, including Sushant Chalise, Rahmad Dawood, Maya Fitria, Agung Setia Budi, Eko Setiawan, and the students from each university.

